

Appendix 5. Secondary outcome measures, demographic data, and potential effect modifiers

The question numbers are those used in the questionnaire (**Appendix 4**).

Perceived benefit and harm of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID

Based on this information

6. What is the effect of wearing glasses is on your chance of getting COVID?

- Lowers chance a lot
- Lowers chance a little
- Has no effect
- Increases the chance a little
- Increases the chance a lot

NOTE: This question is also part of the primary outcome where respondents are asked to rate the certainty of their answer to this question.

9. How likely do you think it is that wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID can cause any important harms?

- Very likely
- Likely
- Unlikely
- Very unlikely

Intended behaviour

Based on this information:

1. If there were a surge of COVID cases in your area, how likely would you be to wear glasses or recommend wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID?

- Very likely
- Likely
- Unlikely
- Very unlikely

5. If there were very few COVID cases in your area, how likely would you be to wear glasses or recommend wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID?

- Very likely
- Likely
- Unlikely
- Very unlikely

Perceptions of the information

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements:

11. This information is a trustworthy summary of what is known about the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

12. This information is a sufficient summary of what is known about the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting COVID.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Please think about the information you just saw about the effects of wearing glasses and the chance of getting COVID.

15. I think the information about whether wearing glasses affects the chance of getting COVID was

- Very clear
- Clear
- Unclear
- Very unclear

16. I think the information about whether wearing glasses to prevent COVID has important harms was

- Very clear
- Clear
- Unclear
- Very unclear

17. Overall, I think the information about wearing glasses to prevent COVID was

- Very helpful
- Helpful
- Unhelpful
- Very unhelpful

18. Say you knew someone who heard that wearing glasses might affect your chance of getting COVID. How likely would you be to share the information you just saw with them?

- Definitely yes
- Probably yes
- Probably no
- Definitely no

Decisional conflict

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements:

2. The decision about wearing glasses if there were a surge of COVID was hard for me to make.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

3. I feel I made an informed decision about wearing glasses if there were a surge of COVID.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

4. I am satisfied with my decision about wearing glasses if there were a surge of COVID.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Demographics

19. Where do you live?

- Norway
- USA

20. What is your age?

- 18-24 years old
- 25-34 years old
- 35-44 years old
- 45-54 years old
- 55-64 years old
- 65-74 years old

21. What is the highest education level you have completed?
- Some secondary/high school
 - Secondary/High school graduate
 - Some college or university
 - College or university graduate
 - Graduate school or professional school graduate

Numeracy

22. A person taking Drug A has a 1% chance of having an allergic reaction. If 1,000 people take Drug A, how many would you expect to have an allergic reaction?

___ person(s) out of 1,000

23. A person taking Drug B has a 1 in 1,000 chance of an allergic reaction. What percent of people taking Drug B will have an allergic reaction?

__ %

24. Imagine that you flip a coin 1,000 times. What is your best guess about how many times the coin would come up heads in 1,000 flips?

___ times out of 1,000

Saliency

22. How worried are you about getting COVID?

- Extremely worried
- Very worried
- Not very worried
- Not worried

23. How important is it for you to take actions to reduce your chance of getting COVID?

- Extremely important
- Very important
- Not very important
- Not important